

REPORT:

A1.2.1: Report on use of heavy-duty hydrogen vehicles in Europe

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Summary This report was written as part of activity 1.2.1 from the EMPIR Metrology for Hydrogen Vehicles 2 (MetroHyVe2) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1 st August 2020 and focused on providing solutions to four measurement challenges faced by the hydrogen industry (flow metering, quality assurance, quality control, sampling and fuel cell stack testing). For more details about this project please visit https://www.sintef.no/projectweb/metrohyve-2/ .	
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1 Introduction

Inability to validate the measurements of hydrogen dispensed at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) is a major barrier to the uptake of hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FCEVs). To address this, several portable primary flow standards were built in the previous MetroHyVe project. These flow standards can be taken to HRS to validate the dispenser measurements and are considered appropriate for “light-duty” vehicle applications, with maximum hydrogen capacities of 2.8 to 6 kg and measurement uncertainty of approximately 0.3% (k=2) in mass.

MetroHyVe II aims to further develop the traceability chain for FCEV refuelling, extending to “heavy-duty” vehicle applications with the introduction of new primary and secondary flow standards. The aim of this report is to review the latest plans for the use of heavy-duty hydrogen fuel cell road vehicles and detail the requirements for new primary flow standards to support their use.

2 Background

For owners of hydrogen vehicles within Europe, there are currently many journeys which cannot be completed due to a lack of available refuelling stations. The development of this refuelling infrastructure is in the early stages. Germany is the furthest ahead, with 99 hydrogen refuelling stations, a relatively small number considering that it has around 15 000 refuelling stations for petrol and diesel vehicles. Other European countries have far fewer HRS. France is second with 26, followed by the UK with 12. The figures for each country are shown in Table 1.

Table 1:HRS by Country

Country	Number of Refuelling stations
Germany	99
France	26
United Kingdom	12
Denmark	8
Austria	6
Netherlands	6
Norway	6
Switzerland	5
Sweden	4
Iceland	3
Italy	3
Spain	3
Belgium	2
Croatia	1
Czech Republic	1
Latvia	1

This appears to be a “chicken and egg” problem, in that there is a lack of incentive to build refuelling stations for such a small user base, but equally people are unlikely to buy hydrogen cars without the assurance that there is sufficient refuelling infrastructure to complete their journeys. One potential solution is through greater utilisation of heavy-duty hydrogen FCEVs. Heavy goods vehicles (HGVs) tend to follow consistent, predictable routes, so potentially fewer refuelling stations are required to facilitate their journeys.

The benefits of hydrogen fuel cell technology are also clearer for larger vehicles compared to light duty transport. Hydrogen has a gravimetric energy density of 140 MJ/kg, this is higher than natural

gas (53.6 MJ/kg), diesel (45.6 MJ/kg), and lithium ion batteries (<5 MJ/kg). In volumetric terms, hydrogen is the least dense gas and takes up more space than both natural gas and diesel. However, when stored as a compressed gas, hydrogen requires about the same amount of space as a battery, for much less weight. Combined with the increased range and shorter refuelling/recharging times, hydrogen fuel cell technology is increasingly competitive with battery technology when moving to larger vehicle sizes.

For these reasons, rather than starting with the passenger vehicle for personal transport, the development of Europe's hydrogen refuelling station infrastructure could be largely driven by the need to service vehicles for haulage, public transport, refuse collection etc. The HRS infrastructure for HGVs can potentially be built at lower overall cost while providing an environment for manufacturers of fuel cells, electrolyzers and refuelling station equipment to further improve their technology and reduce costs, ultimately facilitating greater uptake of light- and heavy-duty FCEVs.

With the expectation that the use of heavy-duty hydrogen fuel cell vehicles will increase significantly in the coming years, it is critical to provide the traceable metrology infrastructure, as was done for light duty vehicles in MetroHyVe. The MetroHyVe II consortium therefore aims to establish a basis of traceability for heavy-duty road vehicle refuelling.

3 Use of Heavy-Duty FCEVs in Europe

3.1 Definition of Heavy-Duty

SAE J2601-1 covers light duty vehicles, with hydrogen storage system sizes from 49.7 to 248.6 L, and includes protocols for two pressure classes (35 and 70 MPa) three fuel delivery temperatures (-40 °C, -30 °C, -20°C) (1.99 kg to 9.94 kg). [1]

SAE J2601-2 covers 35 MPa heavy-duty hydrogen transit buses and vehicles. This is aimed at vehicles with combined hydrogen storage capacity larger than 10 kilograms and is non-prescriptive in how to achieve a full fill in the vehicle tank storage system. [2]

This report considers the refuelling requirements of heavy-duty road vehicles with hydrogen storage capacity of 10 kg or more, primarily trucks and buses. Nominal working pressures include 35 MPa and 70 MPa. In the former case, hydrogen is at the moment not precooled. For the latter, hydrogen is always precooled.

3.2 Heavy Goods Transport

Hydrogen fuel cell technology is particularly well suited for haulage applications where there is a need for long distance transport of heavy goods across routes which are relatively consistent and predictable. The trade body Hydrogen Europe published a position paper in December 2020 estimating the 10 000 hydrogen HGVs could be operating within Europe by 2025 and 100 000 by 2030. [3]

Currently a significant interest in the use for hydrogen FCEV HGVs comes from supermarket chains looking to decarbonise their operations. In one example, four hydrogen FCEV trucks were deployed by the grocery wholesaler ASKO in collaboration with Scania in January 2020 [4]. The internal combustion engine of existing diesel-powered Scania trucks was replaced with an electric drivetrain powered by hydrogen fuel cells, but otherwise the original components were retained. The gross vehicle weight is 26 tonnes + 1 tonne cargo. The hydrogen storage capacity is 33 kg at 35 MPa, providing an estimated range of 400 to 500 km. The trucks are refuelled at the ASKO operated hydrogen refuelling station in Trondheim.

Although Scania has produced both battery and hydrogen fuel cell trucks it has recently stated that it has concluded that hydrogen fuel cells will be too inefficient and expensive for long distance travel. It suggests that up to 3 times as much renewable energy is required to power hydrogen trucks compared to a battery electric truck. The costs associated with repair and maintenance will also be higher in a hydrogen powered vehicle as opposed to a battery powered vehicle. [5] [6]

H2Accelerate is a collaboration between oil companies Shell and OMV and heavy vehicle manufacturers Volve, Daimler and Iveco. The collaboration will involve four elements; green and blue hydrogen production facilities, large scale hydrogen distribution systems; a network of refuelling stations; and fuel-cell trucks. [7] The collaboration expects a proof of concept first stage developing hundreds of hydrogen powered trucks and 20 refuelling stations. In March 2021 Daimler truck AG and Volve Group formed cellcentric, with Volvo group acquiring a 50% share of the partnership for approximately €0.6 billion. [8]

The H2Share project launched in 2017 with the aim of building a 27 ton rigid truck and accompanying mobile H2 refueler. The truck would be built by VDL and the H2 refueler by Wystrach GmbH, followed by testing at six locations in Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium and France. The truck would be fuelled from existing hydrogen refuelling stations in places such as Rhooen and Helmond but would use the mobile H2 refueler in locations where stations were not available. The truck can store a maximum of 30kg hydrogen at 35 MPa with an expected range of 400 km. The road demonstration began in April 2020 in Schelluinen, the Netherlands and moved to Düsseldorf in Germany in December 2020. [9] [10] The truck was tested by transport company ABC Logistik, the company concluded that hydrogen trucks are the future of heavy duty logistics. [11]

In 2019, a joint venture was announced between Hyundai and H2 Energy to provide 1600 hydrogen FCEV trucks to Europe by 2025. A total of 50 were expected to ship in 2020, the first 10 of which were shipped in July [12]. Supermarket chain Migros has taken three of the XCIENT's and plan to measure their performance against both battery-electric and biogas trucks. [13] The Hyundai XCIENT FCEV truck stores hydrogen in seven large tanks at 35 MPa for a total capacity of 34.5 kg hydrogen. The expected range is approximately 400 km, and expected refuelling time is 8 to 20 minutes.

While the most common size for European trials are trucks containing 30 to 40 kg hydrogen at 35 MPa, several manufacturers have announced that they are developing higher capacity trucks. Toyota and Nikola are both developing trucks based on 70 to 80 kg hydrogen storage at 70 MPa. Daimler is also developing a liquid hydrogen system and announced in December 2020 that they would jointly develop the technology for liquid hydrogen refuelling in collaboration with Linde. The Daimler GenH2 truck will begin customer trials in 2023, with the aim to simplify the refuelling process and enable ranges of more than 1000 km on a single fill.¹

In July 2020, Air Liquide announced that they would build Europe's first high pressure refuelling station for long-haul trucks. The refuelling station will be built in 2022 in Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur Region in France and designed to dispense up to 1000 kg/day of hydrogen at 70 MPa. This is targeted at long-haul trucks operating with range up to 800 km on a single fill. In the same month, Air Liquide announced a joint initiative with the Port of Rotterdam Authority with the aim to enable 1000 hydrogen powered low emissions trucks to operate on roads connecting the Netherlands, Belgium and Germany by 2025. This includes the construction of 25 new high capacity hydrogen refuelling stations. Vehicle manufacturers VDL and Nikola are both partners in the project.

¹ Note that liquid hydrogen refuelling is outside the scope of MetroHyVe II.

3.3 Refuse Collection

Another area which could benefit from the use of heavy-duty hydrogen fuel cell vehicles is in refuse collection. Advantages for the haulage sector are still relevant here, the duty cycles of refuse vehicles are characterised by long operating hours and the need to transport heavy payloads. The distances travelled are usually shorter, but the duty cycle includes frequent starting and stopping, particularly for residential routes. An additional incentive in this application is that with close proximity to the public, a greater emphasis is placed on improving air quality.

E-Trucks Europe built an electric refuse truck with a 15 kg (at 35 MPa) hydrogen range extender which was deployed in Groningen, the Netherlands in 2017. E-Trucks Europe subsequently developed models with range extenders of 15 to 30 kg hydrogen capacity. [14] [15]

The EU funded project “Hydrogen Waste Collection Vehicles in North West Europe” (HECTOR) began in January 2019 and will run for 4 years and will deploy 7 hydrogen refuse trucks in 7 pilot sites in North West Europe. The first of these vehicles was deployed in Duisburg, Germany in December 2020. The vehicle stores up to 16.4 kg of hydrogen at 70 MPa, for an estimated range of 285 km. A further 5 trucks are expected to be delivered between February and May 2021. [16]

The FCH JU project “Refuse Vehicle Innovation and Validation in Europe” (REVIVE), running from 2018 to the end of 2021 aims to integrate fuel cell range extenders into 15 existing electric refuse vehicles and deploying them at 8 sites within Europe. The range extender is expected to double the range of these vehicles. The first of these vehicles began operating in Breda, the Netherlands in October 2020.

Ahead of the COP 26 UN climate change summit in Glasgow, the UK government announced funding to provide Glasgow City Council with 19 hydrogen-powered refuse trucks and a refuelling station supplied by green hydrogen. The station will produce green hydrogen from solar and wind power.

3.4 Buses

Of all the proposed uses for heavy duty hydrogen vehicles, buses for public transport are perhaps the closest to commercialisation. Various cities have previously operated trials with hydrogen-powered buses with the aim to provide decarbonised public transport and improve local air quality.

The FCH JU project “Clean Hydrogen in European Cities (CHIC)” ran between 2010 and 2016 and co-funded the deployment of 26 fuel-cell buses in Aargau (CH), Bozen (IT), Milan (IT), London (UK) and Oslo (NO). In addition, 20 buses were deployed in Whistler (Canada). Cologne and Hamburg (DE) operated an additional fleet of 8 buses through separately funded programs. Hydrogen fuel cell buses from 5 manufacturers were operated: Wrightbus, EvoBus, Van Hool, Solaris and Phileas. These all operated with 35 MPa tanks and 33 – 35 kg total hydrogen capacity. On top of the 54 fuel cell buses, 4 hydrogen internal combustion engine (ICE) buses were operated in Berlin until 2014. [17] [18] [19] The project was considered a success meeting most of the project objectives and technical goals with hydrogen powered buses operating for more than 519,000 hours and travelling a total distance of 9,600,00 km during the lifetime of the project. [20]

The FCH JU funded project “Joint Initiative for hydrogen Vehicles across Europe” (JIVE) started in 2017 and running to 2023 aims to deploy 139 fuel cell buses and associated infrastructure in Denmark, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands and the UK. Together with JIVE2, the two projects aim to operate a fleet of nearly 300 zero emission fuel cell buses and associated infrastructure by the early 2020's in 22 cities across Europe. The projects also aim to reduce the overall maximum price of a fuel cell bus to €625K. [21]

In 2018, a total of 40 hydrogen fuel cell buses were ordered from the Belgian manufacturer Van Hool for operation in two German cities, 30 were provided to Cologne and 10 to Wuppertal. [22] Both fleets

will be expanded in 2021 with buses from Solaris, 15 of which will be provided to Cologne, 10 to Wuppertal. [23] In December 2020, Van Hool announced that its fuel cell buses had travelled a total combined distance of 10 million kilometres with 141 vehicles being sold. [24]

As of September 2020, Sustainable Bus magazine reported that 143 hydrogen fuel cell buses have been deployed and operated in Europe, with a further 1079 expected by 2025. It has been estimated that a minimum of 22.5% of all new buses ordered in 2021 across Europe will have to be zero emission to comply with current legislation. [25] The cost of each bus was estimated at £500 000, a substantial reduction since the CHIC project (approximately 1.5M EUR per bus). Various sources have indicated a target cost of 350 000 EUR per bus and hydrogen price of £5 to £7 per kg is required in order to compete with standard diesel buses. [19] [26]

Figure 1: Evolution of fuel cell bus costs in Europe [19]

In 2019, the H2Bus Consortium was formed between many leading players in the hydrogen fuel cell bus supply chain; Everfuel, Wrightbus, Ballard Power Systems, Hexagon Composites, Nel Hydrogen and Ryse Hydrogen. The aim of the consortium is to deploy 1 000 fuel cell buses, and the required supporting infrastructure in European cities at commercially competitive rates. The first phase will be the deployment of 600 buses by 2023. The consortium is coordinated by Element Energy, who also had a coordinating role in the FCH JU-funded JIVE project. The consortium is offering buses with claimed ranges in excess of 450 km. Crucially, the consortium is aiming to achieve price competitiveness with diesel buses, with the price of the single deck bus at less than 375 000 EUR and green hydrogen supplied at €5/kg to €7/kg.

In May 2020 Wrightbus announced plans to introduce a further 3000 hydrogen buses to the UK by the year 2024. 15 of the double-decker version of the Wrightbus Streetdeck bus were provided to Aberdeen City Council in October 2020, with a further 10 ordered in 2021. [27] [28] 20 each have been ordered by both Birmingham City Council and Transport for London. [29] [30]

3.5 Summary of Vehicle Operating Ranges

HGVs powered by hydrogen fuel cells are increasingly common in Europe and may be the best route to development of the refuelling infrastructure which would ultimately support the use of FCEVs at other size ranges. The most common vehicle sizes are equipped with 32 kg H2 capacity at 35 MPa

pressure, providing a range of up to 400 km. However, higher capacity HGV vehicles are used in other countries such as USA and Japan, with H₂ capacity up to 80 kg at 70 MPa and range up to 800 km. It is possible that the higher capacity 70 MPa trucks could be used in Europe. Recently, companies (Air Liquide) and authorities (Dutch port) have announced plans to support the larger duty HGVs.

Table 2: Summary of Hydrogen Fuel Cell Vehicle Operating Ranges

Heavy Goods Transport			
Manufacturer	Model	Range	H₂ Stored
Hyundai	Xcient Fuel Cell [31]	400 km	34.5 kg at 35 MPa
VDL	[32]	400 km	30 kg at 35 MPa
ESORO	[33]	375 to 400 km	31 kg at 35 MPa
Scania	[34]	400 to 500 km	33 kg at 35 MPa
Toyota	Hino Profia FR1AWHG [35]	600 km	60 kg at 70 MPa
Nikola	Nikola One Nikola Two [36] [37]	1100 km	80 kg at 70 MPa
Daimler Mercedes Benz	GenH2 [38]	1000 km	Cryogenic Liquid
Refuse Vehicles			
Manufacturer	Model	Range	H₂ Stored
E-Trucks Europe	H2 Hydrogen-ready [14]		15 kg to 30 kg range extended
Geesinknorba	[39]	285 km	16.4 kg at 70 MPa
ULEMCo [40]			Diesel/hydrogen hybrid conversions
Buses			
Manufacturer	Model	Range	H₂ Stored
Wrightbus	Double Deck [41]	350 km	30 kg at 35 MPa
Van Hool [42] [43]	A330 Fuel Cell	350 km	38.2 kg at 35 MPa
Solaris [44]	Urbino 12	350 km	37 kg at 35 MPa
EvoBus	[17]		35 kg at 35 MPa

4 Requirements for calibration and validation of a HRS from OIML R139-2:2018

When a hydrogen station operator wishes to sell its product to customers, the station manufacturer must comply with the associated standards regarding resale of energy to individuals (legal metrology) to ensure reliability and fairness in the transaction. There is little information regarding the sale of hydrogen (HRS) to individuals. However, the “Organisation Internationale de Métrologie Légale - OIML” has a recommendation on compressed gas (natural gas mainly) which has recently been revised in order to integrate the technical constraints to the use of hydrogen. The most recent edition which was issued in October 2018 has 3 parts which are available on the OIML website. https://www.oiml.org/en/files/pdf_r/r138-p-e07.pdf

The text is divided into three parts, constituting three separate documents:

1. R139-1 - Metrological and Technical Requirements (52 pages) [45]
2. R139-2 - Metrological controls and performance tests (63 pages) [46]
3. R139-3 - Test Report Format (65 pages) [47]

4.1.1 Metrological and technical requirements (document R139-1)

This first section describes the elements that constitute the measurement system and therefore items that need to be tested for certification of the measuring system.

Figure 2 below summarizes the mandatory and optional elements.

Figure 2: Constituents of a typical compressed gaseous fuel measuring system for vehicles.

Metrological obligations for the measurement system:

This section lists (in no order of importance) all mandatory metrological requirements to obtain OIML R139 certification: 2018 for a HRS at 70 MPa. Metrological requirements not applicable to hydrogen are not noted (for example, those applying to CNG only).

1. The Maximum Permissible Error (MPE) is defined in the Table 3 below:

Accuracy class		MPE for the meter [in % of the measured quantity value]	MPE for the complete measuring system [in % of the measured quantity value]	
			at type evaluation, initial or subsequent verification	in-service inspection under rated operating conditions
For general application	1.5	1	1.5	2
For hydrogen only	2	1.5	2	3
	4	2	4	5

Table 3: MPE values

There are 2 main categories in this table, the MPE for the meter itself (on the left side) and the MPE for the complete measuring system.

It is important to note that there are 2 classes for hydrogen. Class 4 will be mainly accepted for existing stations whereas class 2 shall be chosen for new HRS. As an example, the MPE during a type approval of a new HRS (class 2) is 2%.

- In the case of the measurement of the 'smallest measurable amount' (MMQ) (Minimum Measured Quantity) , the MPE is twice the value of the Table 3 above as shown in Section 5.2.3 of the OIML standrad. [45]

$$E_{min} = 2 \times MMQ \times R_{MPE}$$

Where:

R_{MPE} = The maximum premissable error ratio according to Section 5.2.1 [45] MMQ
= The specified minimum measured quantity accoridng to Section 5.3.2. [45]

$$E_{min} = 2 \times MMQ \times R_{MPE} \text{ [g; kg]}$$

where: R_{MPE} = the maximum permissible error ratio according to 5.2.1
(in 5.2.1 expressed in percentages of the measured quantity value);

MMQ = the specified minimum measured quantity according to 5.3.2.

The MMQ has been defined as a fixed value for all hydrogen applications whereas it was a function of the mass flow rate for other compressed gas fuels. It is stated in OIML R139:2018 that the maximum MMQ for all types of HRS is **1 kg**. Section 5.3.2.2 [45]

4.1.2 OIML R139-2 Metrological control and performance tests

Part 2 of the OIML R139 recommendation [46] relates to the metrological controls, instrument evaluation, type evaluation, and the initial and subsequent verifications of a HRS. For metrological controls, most of the section is devoted to the uncertainty calculations. The uncertainty requirements depend on the type of certification, and are related to the MPE of the HRS. For instrument evaluation, the recommendation details instrument specifications and meter capacity, as well as flow rate. The specific tests to be performed as part of an evaluation are detailed, and denoted as test # 4, #5 and # 7 as described in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4: Initial settings for tests on systems without sequential control

Test #	Initial state
Test 4	Initial test receiver pressure of 0 kPa or higher if so required for safety reasons Initial station storage pressure at P_{st}
Test 5	Initial test receiver pressure of $0.5 P_v$ Initial station storage pressure at P_{st}

Table 5: Initial settings for tests on systems with and without sequential control

Test #	Initial state
Test 7 (minimum measured quantity)	The conditions for test 3 or 6 are adapted in order to test the minimum measured quantity. For this purpose, the pressure does not have to be P_v in the test receiver at the end, but may be any pressure (as close as practical to P_v) such that the quantity of transferred gas shall be at least the minimum measured quantity.

P_{st} maximum storage pressure

P_v max allowable vehicle fast fill pressure

Figure 3: Test Required by OIML 139

5 Requirements for the Primary Flow Standards

In the coming years, there is likely to be a significant increase in the use of hydrogen FCEV vehicles in the heavy-duty range. There will therefore be a need to provide the metrological infrastructure to validate the hydrogen dispensed from refuelling stations for vehicles in this size range.

5.1 Limitations of existing flow standards

The existing primary flow standards developed for light duty vehicles cannot be used for the vehicles in this range, for several reasons.

Due to limited tank capacity (up to 150 litres) of the existing flow standards, the refuelling station Coriolis meters operate at flow rates less than 3.6 kg/min during evaluations. Flow rates of up to 7.2 kg/min are expected for refuelling of buses and trucks, depending if pre-cooling is applied or not. Like most flow meter types, the Coriolis meter response is more stable at medium to high flow rates. This could result in performance differences in the flow meter, depending on the size of vehicle being refuelled.

A major contribution to measurement error in HRS is the change in pressure and density in piping connection the dispenser to a flow meter installed upstream. This 'dead volume' effect is unrelated to the flow meter behaviour and the relative contribution is reduced when filling larger vessels to higher hydrogen capacity. Therefore, using a light duty standard to assess the HRS accuracy for heavy duty refuelling could result in over-estimated errors.

Similarly, the HRS Coriolis meter can be greatly influenced by temperature effects if it is installed in the cold region of the HRS. From MetroHyVe 1, it was observed that low temperature effects are only moderate if the temperature is stable and flow rates are relatively high. The real concern is transient temperature effects, as a meter which is initially at ambient temperature is cooled by the incoming stream of hydrogen at -40°C during the refuelling process.

This temperature effect will be reduced for heavy duty vehicle refuelling, for two reasons. Many heavy-duty vehicles are limited to 35 MPa filling pressures. There is a reduced requirement for pre-cooling compared to 70 MPa service. For refuelling of these vehicles, there will typically be less of an initial temperature difference between the flow meter and the incoming gas and therefore less opportunity for transient temperature effects to occur. Also, regardless of the vehicle filling pressure (35 MPa or 70 MPa) heavy duty refuelling occurs at higher flow rates and for longer durations than light duty. Therefore, a greater proportion of the hydrogen should be metered at high flow rates and stable temperatures compared to a light duty refuelling.

To conclude, using a light duty primary standard is likely to overestimate errors for heavy-duty vehicle refuelling, due to a greater influence of low flow rate, low temperature and dead volume effects. For a robust evaluation of HRS accuracy in heavy-duty vehicle refuelling, new flow standards are required.

5.2 Operating limits

The heavy-duty HRS primary standards need to have sufficient hydrogen capacity to represent the vehicles that the HRS will service. However, matching the vehicle capacities on a 1:1 basis is impractical. Currently, there is a greater prevalence of heavy-duty vehicles designed for 35 MPa service and hydrogen capacity of 30 to 40 kg in Europe. However other territories including North America and Asia favour the larger capacity HGVs based on 70 to 80 kg hydrogen storage at 70 MPa, and there are some early indications that Europe could follow suit.

If the primary standards built matched these vehicle sizes exactly, then two very different systems would be required. Even the smaller 40 kg version would be extremely expensive to build, difficult to

transport and operate, and achieving a reasonable measurement uncertainty of less than 0.5% may not be feasible.

For context, a light duty (4 to 6 kg) primary standard with measurement uncertainty of about 3 g (0.3 % for 1 kg) weighs about 500 kg, could be transported by a small van and costs about 300k EUR to build. A heavy-duty standard with 40 kg hydrogen capacity could weigh more than 2000 kg and cost more than 1M EUR to build. The measurement uncertainty achievable will be higher compared to the light duty standards, as the available weighing scales and load cells suitable for this range have poorer resolution, while the MMQ for heavy duty vehicles is still 1 kg, despite the higher maximum capacity. Moreover, buoyancy correction will have a larger contribution due to the larger size of the pressure tanks and the control of the temperature gradient around the scales will be key to limit the measurement uncertainty.

Instead, the project partners intend to build flow standards which do not match the vehicle capacities on a 1:1 basis, but still operate at representative fuelling conditions and are suitable to perform OIML R 139 evaluation.

The flow standards produced from this project will meet the following requirements:

- Maximum hydrogen capacity of at least 10 kg (SAE J601-2 specifies 10 kg and above for heavy-duty vehicles)
- Measurement uncertainty of 0.5% or better (required by JRP protocol)
- Average flow rate of 1.8 kg/min or higher (required by JRP protocol)
- At least 2 kg hydrogen transferred for a half fill, 17.5 to 35 MPa (required by OIML R 139)

5.3 Estimation of Required volumes

Table 4 gives the pressure ranges for testing a HRS according to OIML R139. For test 4 and 5, the delivered quantity should always be above twice the MMQ, which yields a minimal delivered mass of 2 kg for these tests. The delivered mass into a tank after a refuelling can be calculated using Equ. 1.

$$m = V_{tank} \cdot (\rho_{H2,f} - \rho_{H2,i}) \quad (1)$$

where

V_{tank} : tank volume,

$\rho_{H2,x}$: final and initial hydrogen density in the tank after and before the refuelling.

One can now estimate the minimum required tank volume of a gravimetric system to perform tests according to OIML R139 for a 35 MPa HRS. The hydrogen density is calculated using a formula provided by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [48]. Estimates are presented in Table 6, where assumptions on initial and final temperatures and pressures were made. One finds out that a tank volume of approximately 270 L on the gravimetric standard is needed to accommodate 2 kg of hydrogen for Test 5. This should be considered as an indicative value and is strongly dependent on initial and final pressure and temperature conditions in the tank.

Table 6: Tank volume estimates for testing a 35 MPa HRS.

Test	Mass H ₂	Initial pressure (MPa)	Initial density (kg/m ³)	Final pressure (MPa)	Final density (kg/m ³)	Initial tank temperature (°C)	Final tank temperature (°C)	Required volume (L)
4	2 kg	3.0	2.48	35.0	20.70	15.0	70.0	110
5	2 kg	17.5	13.27	35.0	20.70	15.0	70.0	269
5	2 kg	17.5	13.49	35.0	20.70	10.0	70.0	277
5	2 kg	15.0	11.55	35.0	20.70	15.0	70.0	219

For the sake of the argument, one will consider a conservative tank volume of 300 L on the gravimetric standard to be able to perform all the tests from Table 4 and Table 5 for a 35 MPa HRS. This tank would contain around 6 kg of hydrogen at 35 MPa.

5.4 Estimation of Achievable flow rates

Flow rate in a dispenser is generated by a pressure ramp rate (PRR). The average mass flow rate during delivery to the vehicle can be estimated using

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \frac{V_{tank}}{\Delta t} \cdot (\rho_{H_2,f} - \rho_{H_2,i}) \quad (2)$$

where

V_{tank} : tank volume,

Δt : refuelling time,

$\rho_{H_2,x}$: final and initial hydrogen density in the tank after and before the refuelling.

The fuelling time can be estimated using tabulated PRR values from SAE J2601 as well as temperature and pressure conditions. PRR values for 35 MPa at ambient temperature are not included in SAE J2601, a conservative value of 3 MPa/min is considered here.

Mass flow rate estimates for various refuelling scenarios are presented in Table 8. The following assumptions have been made:

- Initial tank and hydrogen temperature: 15 °C
- Initial tank pressure: 3 MPa → density of hydrogen : 2.48 kg/m³
- Final tank and hydrogen temperature: 70 °C
- Final tank pressure: 35 MPa or 70 MPa → density of hydrogen: 20.7 kg/m³ or 35.5 kg/m³ respectively
- No communication between dispenser and vehicle

This will yield conservative mass flow rates. Tank volumes in SAE J2601 are separated into categories (A through D), see Table 7, and have an impact on PRR.

Table 7: Table 4 from SAE J2601, May 2020.

Table 4 - CHSS capacity categories

Pressure Class	Total Amount of Hydrogen in CHSS at 100% SOC (kg)	Water Volume of CHSS (L)	CHSS Capacity Category Identifier
H35	1.19 to 2.39	49.7 to 99.4	A
H35	2.39 to 4.18	99.4 to 174.0	B
H35	4.18 to 5.97	174.0 to 248.6	C
H70	2.00 to 4.00	49.7 to 99.4	A
H70	4.00 to 7.00	99.4 to 174.0	B
H70	7.00 to 10.00	174.0 to 248.6	C
H70	>10.00	>248.6	D

Table 8: Mass flow rate estimates for various refuelling scenarios.

Pressure class	Temperature class	Tank volume (Category) (L)	PRR (MPa/min)	H2 mass (kg)	Filling time (min)	Average mass flow rate (kg/min)
H35	Ambient	300.0	3.0	5.47	10.7	0.51
H35	Ambient	200.0	3.0	3.64	10.7	0.34
H35	Ambient	1103	3.0	20.1	10.7	1.80
H35	Ambient	2102	3.0	38.3	10.7	3.58
H70	T40	100.0 (B)	21.8	3.31	3.07	1.08
H70	T40	200.0 (C)	19.9	6.61	3.37	1.96
H70	T40	300.0 (D)	19.9	9.92	3.37	2.95
H70	T40	360.0 (D)	19.9	11.90	3.37	3.53

One notices that a tank volume of 300 L, as estimated in section 5.3, would result in an average mass flow rate of 0.51 kg/min with a H35 pressure class at ambient conditions (15 °C). This is much lower than the requirement from the JRP protocol of 50% of maximum flow rate. To reach a mass flow rate of 1.8 kg/min would require a tank volume of approximately 1000 L.

To reach a mass flow rate of 1.8 kg/min with a H70 pressure class and precooled hydrogen at – 40 °C would require a tank volume of approximately 200 L.

Section 3 indicates that the most common heavy-duty vehicles have hydrogen capacities of around 32 kg at 35 MPa and 15°C, this yields a tank volume of 1333 L and average mass flow rates during refuelling from 2.1 kg/min up to 3.2 kg/min.

5.5 Recommendation

At the basis of this work package is an understanding that for the largest duty ranges, building primary flow standards which match the capacity of the vehicle on a 1:1 basis will not always be practical, and the metrological infrastructure may need to be scaled up using secondary flow standards and master meters which are traceable to smaller primary standards.

It is therefore proposed that two primary standards are built for heavy-duty vehicle service. Due to cost, weight, and measurement uncertainty considerations, these will both be in the 10 to 30 kg range. One will be built for maximum pressures of 35 MPa, the other for 70 MPa.

Two portable primary flow standards are proposed for heavy-duty refuelling:

Table 9: Mass flow rate estimates for various refuelling scenarios.

NMI/DI	Pressure Class	Tank Volume	H ₂ capacity at 350 bar	H ₂ capacity at 700 bar	Average flow rate (kg/min)	
					3 MPa/min, no pre-cooling	20 MPa/min with pre-cooling
NEL	35 MPa	1050 L	25.2 kg	-	1.8	-
METAS	70 MPa	600 L	14.4 kg	24.5 kg	1.02	6.8

With the development of these new standards, it will be possible to evaluate refuelling stations with both a light duty standard (up to 6 kg, 70 MPa) followed by a heavy-duty standard (>10 kg, 35 MPa). Comparing the results would allow the investigators to determine the sensitivity of various influences (influence of dead volume effect, average flow rate and temperature sensitivity), ultimately supporting the use of calibrated secondary standards for scale-up to very large applications (trains, marine transport, aircraft).

For example, by selecting a refuelling station where the Coriolis meter is installed at the cold region, the influence of dead volume will be removed and it will be possible to isolate the influence of rapid temperature variations on overall billing accuracy, by comparing results from both the light and heavy duty flow standards. It is already expected that errors caused by temperature effects will be reduced for refuelling of larger vehicles, but this approach would provide the necessary data and evidence.

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